

Successful Management of Vascular Cognitive Impairment In Ischemic Stroke with Haemodilution: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT Background: Stroke is a neurovascular disorder with focal or global deficit neurology. Cognitive Impairment is non-motoric symptoms and rare manifestation during acute phase stroke. **Report:** We report a patient with Ischemic stroke with family's to complain of sudden onset recent memory loss, confusing and headache. The Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) showed moderate cognitive impairment. Computed tomography scan (CT-scan) of his brain showed temporoparietal infark. Patient with high-level haematocrit. He was treated with aspillets and haemodilution. The patient was symptomatically better after 6 hours. **Conclusion:** Stroke ischemic acute with high haematocrit, with isovolemic haemodilution blood-HES, exchanged therapy gives a good outcome in cognitive function.

KEYWORDS Cognitive impairment, acute phase stroke, haemodilution

Introduction

Stroke is a medical emergency in neurology. Early neurological deterioration or death occurs in 24 hours. Clinical manifestation of stroke may vary depending on the vascular lesion. Hypertension, diabetic, dyslipidemia, hematocrit level are the significant risk in stroke. Hematocrit is essential to rule in blood viscosity and the proportion by volume. Its considered with haemoglobin, white blood cell, and platelet count. Hematite level influences cerebral blood flow by poor arterial oxygen delivery and correlates inversely. [1]. Cognitive impairment is affected by vascular pathology in the brain. 10 % of Patients with cognitive impairment occurred before the first stroke attack.[2] There are limited

published data on the use of haemodilution in the treatment of VCI in high-level haematocrit.

Case presentation

A 72 years old male presented to Public General Hospital Sanglah Denpasar, Bali. Informed consent was received from the patient involved in this case study. He had complained sudden onset recent memory loss, confusing and headache of 29 hours duration. Informed consent was received from the patient involved in this case study. He has diagnosed with stroke non-haemorrhagic thrombus and was on the drug (antiplatelet aggregation aspilet and citicoline). On physical examination, blood pressure 140/80 mmHg, he was in disorientation, confusion, headache (NPRS =3). The meningeal sign is negative, no motoric weakness, no cranial nerves palsy, absent pathological reflex. Cognitive screening tool with MMSE shown moderate cognitive impairment (score 13).

Laboratory investigation showed 16.54 g/dL, total white blood cell count 7.30x10⁹/L, platelet count 310 x10⁹/L, haematocrit 53.94%. Serum electrolytes, blood sugar, renal and liver function test were normal. Chest X-ray is normal. Computed tomography scan of the brain showed subacute infark left temporoparietal region (Fig. 1).

The patients were treated with single haemodilution isov-

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Figure 1: The Brain CT-scan without contrast showing less than 24 hours, hypodense lesion in the left temporoparietal region.

olemic with the blood-HES exchange of 350 ml in the emergency neurology department. The antiplatelet drug was given 320mg followed by 80 mg daily. His symptoms gradually better within 12 hours of admission. The hematocrit level 46% decrease after haemodilution. The MMSE improved to mild cognitive impairment(score 23). After five days, patients were discharged from hospital in an ambulatory state. He was advised to continue the antiplatelet drug.

Discussion

Stroke is non-infection disease occurred in older adults with dysfunction of the brain due to cerebral blood flow impairment.[3] Ras, age; gender is an unmodified risk factor. The primary clinical features of stroke are hemiparesis, speech disturbances, hemianopsia, hemihypesthesia, and cranial nerve palsies.[4,5]

In this case, VCI occurs in the acute phase of stroke. This is very different from the research conducted by Lisa Mellon et al., who found that 50% of VCI patients occur after stroke in 6 months.[2] Research conducted by Jia Hao Sun et al. found VCI patients to occur within three months after stroke.[3] The underlying mechanism is by a study conducted by Jia Hao Sun et al. That infarct volume was associated with > 100 ml VCI events causing dementia.[3]The presence of lesions in the frontal cortex, limbic area and white matter decreases half of the variability in MMSE counting. The limbic system area includes hippocampus and the entorhinal cortex.[3] Lesions in the right hippocampus will cause persistent long-term memory impairment, while infarction in the left hippocampus, impact nonverbal long-term memory.[3] Dyslipidemia and diabetes mellitus are associated with the incidence of hippocampal atrophy in the male population. The study conducted by Gemmel et al. investigation of the post mortem hippocampus in post-stroke dementia patients. The volume of neurons is 10-20% smaller in the CA1 and CA2 areas, 20% smaller than the CA3 and CA4 areas. Li et al. Also found blockages in the cerebral artery media in animal model related to the incidence of post-stroke VCI through the mechanism of increasing levels of GABAergic neurotransmitters and decreasing extracellular regulated protein kinase (ERK) extracellular regulation.[3] Decreasing ERK function causes failure of hydrogen sulfide donors which are a neurotransmitter to inhibit damage neurons hippocampally.[3]

In this case, using isovolemia hemodilution with Hydroxyethyl Strach (HES) replacement fluid according to the volume of blood taken 350ml exchange with HES.[6,7,8] We choose HES because it does not impair kidney function, but the most signifi-

cant advantage is disrupted platelet function. The mechanism that explains HES inhibits platelet function through "platelet-linking von Willebrand factor, decreases the amount of fibrinogen, thrombin generation, and reduce platelet-fibrinogen surface receptor (glycoprotein IId and IIIa).[9]

Blood flow velocity in cerebral arteries undergoes improvement in tissue perfusion due to a decrease in hematocrit from 53,39% to 46% normal levels and the effect of HES to inhibition of thrombus formation. Clinical changes in patients are characterized by the discovery of improved cognitive function by scoring MMSE 13 to 23. [10]

Conclusion

Stroke ischemic acute with high haematocrit, with isovolemic haemodilution blood-HES, exchanged therapy gives a good outcome in cognitive function.

Competing Interests

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References

1. Canan, Tagay Isikay., Nevzat, Uzuner., Demet, Gucuyener., Gazi, Ozdemir. The effect of hematocrite and age on transcranial Doppler measurements in patients with recent ischemic stroke. *Neurology Indian* March 2005 Vol 53 Issue 1.
2. Lisa, Mellon., Linda, Brewer., Patricia, Hall., Frances, Horgan., David, Williams., Anne, Hickey. Cognitive impairment six months after ischaemic stroke: a profile from APIRE-S Study. *BMC Neurol*: 2015;15:31.
3. Jia, Hao., Sun, Lee Tan., Jin, Tai Yu. Post stroke cognitive impairment: epidemiology, mechanisms, and management. *Ann Trans Med* 2014;2(8):80.

4. Jane, Nakibuuka., Martha, Sajatovic., Joaniter, Nankabirwa1., Charles, Ssendikadiwa., Anthony J, Furlan., Elly, Katabira1., James, Kayima1., Nelson, Kalema., Jayne Byakika., Tusiime., and Edward Ddumba. Early mortality and functional outcome after acute stroke in Uganda: prospective study with 30 day follow-up. Nakibuuka et al. SpringerPlus (2015) 4:450.
5. Zehra Bozdoğan, Aslihan Taşkiran Sağ, Zeynep Neşe Öztekin, Fikri Ak. Posterior Cerebral Artery Infarction with Cognitive Findings: More Than Hemianopia. Turkish Journal of Neurology 2013; 19: 139-142.
6. Timothy S Chang¹ and Matthew B Jensen. Haemodilution for acute ischaemic stroke. Cochrane Database Syst Rev. Author manuscript; available in PMC 2015 August 27.
7. Kyung Hee Kim, Ki Young Oh. Clinical applications of therapeutic phlebotomy. Journal of Blood Medicine 2016:7.
8. S. Bengeri. Effect of Hydroxyethyl starch in critically ill patients. British Journal of Anaesthesia 2007;98 (6): 841–848.
9. Gisela, Scharbert., Engelbert, Deusch., Hans, Georg Kress., Manfred, Greher., Burkhard, Gustorff., and Sibylle A., Kozek, Langenecker. Inhibition of Platelet Function by Hydroxyethyl Starch Solutions in Chronic Pain Patients Undergoing Peridural Anesthesia. AnesthAnalg 2004;99:823–7.
10. Canan Togay Isikay, Nevzat Uzuner, Demet Gucuyener, Gazi Ozdemir. The effect of hematocrit and age on transcranial Doppler measurements in patients with recent ischemic stroke. Neurology Indian March;2005:53(1).